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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
CISPLATIN-LOADED NEOSOMES FOR TARGETED DRUG
DELIVERY****J. Prathyusha¹, Gudigopuram Deepthi², G. Lavanya³, D. Vasanth Kumar³, E. Poojitha³,
J Bhupesh³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sree Dattha Institute of Pharmacy, Sheriguda (V), Ibrahimpatnam (M), Ranga Reddy, Telangana, India²Assistant Professor, Department of PAQA, Sree Dattha Institute of Pharmacy, Sheriguda (V), Ibrahimpatnam (M), Ranga Reddy, Telangana, India³Department of Pharmaceutics, Sree Dattha Institute of Pharmacy, Sagar Road, Sheriguda, Ibrahimpatnam, Telangana, India**Abstract:**

The present study was focused on formulating and evaluating Cisplatin containing niosomal formulation for in vitro studies. Niosomal formulations were prepared by using different ratio of surfactant (Tweens and Spans grades 20, 20) and cholesterol by the thin film hydration method and were evaluated for in vitro characteristics, stability studies. Span 20 containing niosomal formulation displayed highest entrapment efficiency with desired particle size. SEM analyses showed that niosomal formulation was spherical in shape. Niosomes containing Span 20 displayed higher percentage of drug release after 8 h as compared to other formulations. F-4 formulation was found to be stable at the end of the study on storage condition. The present study suggested that niosomal formulations provide sustained and prolonged delivery of drug with enhance bioavailability.

Keywords: niosomes, Cisplatin, bioavailability, thin film hydration technique, in vitro drug release studies.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

During the past decade formulation of vesicles as a tool to improve drug delivery, has created a lot of interest amongst the scientist working in the area of drug delivery systems. Vesicular system such as liposomes, niosomes, transferosomes, pharmacosomes and ethosomes provide an alternative to improve the drug delivery.¹ Niosomes play an important role owing to their nonionic properties, in such drug delivery system. Design and development of novel drug delivery system (NDDS) has two prerequisites.² First, it should deliver the drug in accordance with a predetermined rate and second it should release therapeutically effective amount of drug at the site of action.³ Conventional dosage forms are unable to meet these requisites. Niosomes are essentially non-ionic surfactant based multilamellar or unilamellar vesicles in which an aqueous solution of solute is entirely enclosed by a membrane resulting from the organization of surfactant macromolecules as bilayer.⁴ Niosomes are formed on hydration of non-ionic surfactant film which eventually hydrates imbibing or encapsulating the hydrating aqueous solution. The main aim of development of niosomes is to control the release of drug in a sustained way, modification of distribution profile of drug and for targeting the drug to the specific body site.⁵ Niosome are non-ionic surfactant vesicles obtained by hydrating mixture of cholesterol and nonionic surfactants. It can be used as carriers of amphiphilic and lipophilic drug. In niosomes drug delivery system, the medication is encapsulated in a vesicle. Niosomes are biodegradable, biocompatible non-immunogenic and exhibit flexibility in their structural characterization.⁶ The main object of this review the application of niosomes technology is used to treat a number of diseases, niosomes have good opportunity in research and beneficial for researcher and pharma industries.⁷

2.1 MATERIALS

cisplatin was collected as a gift sample from Hetero laboratories, Hyderabad, Synthetic polymers, super disintegrants and other excipients were purchased from AR chemicals.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

Formulation development

Table-1: Composition of Niosomal Cisplatin (F1 to F4)

S.No.	Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Cisplatin	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
2	Cholesterol	50	50	50	50
2	Span 20	20	40	-	-
3	Tween 20	-	-	20	40

Preparation of niosomes

In this method the lipids were dissolved in chloroform. This solution of lipids in chloroform was spread over flat bottom conical flask. The solution was then evaporated at room temperature without disturbing the solution. The hydration of lipid film form was carried out with aqueous medium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). For this the flask was inclined to one side and aqueous medium containing drug to be entrapped was introduced down the side of flask and flask was slowly returned to upright orientation. The fluid was allowed to run gently over lipid layer and flask was allowed to stand for 2 h at 37°C for complete swelling. After swelling, vesicles are harvested by swirling the contents of flask to yield milky white suspension. Then formulations were subjected to centrifugation. Then formulations were subjected to centrifugation. Different batches of niosomes were prepared in order to select an optimum formula⁸.

FT-IR study⁹

Compatibility studies of cisplatin and the disintegrants were carried out by using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Fourier transform infrared spectra of the samples were obtained in the range of 4000 to 450 cm⁻¹ using a FTIR by the KBr disc method

Evaluations of niosomes^{10,11,12,13}

Particle size analysis

All the prepared batches of niosomes were viewed under microscope to study their size. Size of vesicles from each batch was measured at different location on slide by taking a small drop of niosomal dispersion on it and average size of niosomes vesicles were determined.

Drug entrapment efficiency of niosomes

Entrapment efficiency of niosomes were determined by centrifugation method. Aliquots (1 ml) of niosomal dispersion were subjected to centrifugation on a laboratory centrifuge (Remi R4C) at 3500 rpm for a period of 90 min. The clear supernatants were removed carefully to separate non entrapped Cisplatin and absorbance recorded at 203 nm. The sediment in the centrifugation tube was diluted to 100 ml with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and the absorbance of this solution was recorded at 203 nm.

Amount of Cisplatin in supernatant and sediment gave a total amount of Cisplatin in 1 ml dispersion. % entrapment of drug was calculated by the following formula

% Drug Entrapped (PDE) =
Amount of drug/ Total amount of drug /in
sediment X 100

***In Vitro* Drug release study**

The release studies were carried out in 10 ml Franz diffusion cell containing 10 ml Phosphate buffer. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (10ml) was placed in a 10 ml beaker. The beaker was assembled on a magnetic stirrer and the medium was equilibrated at $37 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. Dialysis membrane was taken and one end of the membrane was sealed. After separation of non entrapped Cisplatin Niosomal dispersion was filled in the dialysis membrane and other end was closed. The dialysis membrane containing the sample was suspended in the medium. 1ml of aliquots were withdrawn at specific intervals, filtered after withdrawal and the apparatus was immediately replenished with same quantity of fresh buffer medium.

Stability studies¹⁴

The success of an effective formulation can be evaluated only through stability studies. The purpose of stability testing is to obtain a stable product which assures its safety and efficacy up to the end of shelf life at defined storage conditions and peak profile. The prepared Cisplatin niosomes were placed on plastic tubes containing desiccant and stored at ambient conditions, such as at room temperature, $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and refrigerator $2-8^\circ\text{C}$ for a period of 90 days.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Drug - excipient compatibility studies (FT-IR)

The compatibility between the drug and the selected lipid and other excipients was evaluated using FTIR peak matching method. There was no appearance or disappearance of peaks in the drug-lipid mixture, which confirmed the absence of any chemical interaction between the drug, lipid and other chemicals.

Fig- : 1 FTIR Studies of Pure Drug (Cisplatin)

Fig - : 2 FTIR Studies of Optimization

Particle size

Vesicle shape: Vesicle shape of the prepared formulation was found to be spherical from the SEM(scanning electron microscope) analysis at 15.00kV

Fig:-3 Particle size of optimization formulation

Table: 2 Mean particle size (mps) of different formulation of niosomes

Sr. No	Formulation No.	Particle size(µm)
1	F1	210
2	F2	198
3	F3	209
4	F4	219

Drug entrapment efficiency

Table- : 3 Different batches of niosome made by using different ratio of lipids

Sr. No	Formulation no.	PDE
1	F1	66.12
2	F2	74.54
3	F3	71.13
4	F4	84.52

Drug release studies

Table-: 4 Cumulative percentage drug release from various formulation of niosomes

Time	Batch code			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	15.25	18.95	16.50	17.25
2	22.10	22.65	21.18	20.18
3	34.26	37.21	38.30	31.12
4	40.52	45.31	44.35	42.28
5	52.85	61.52	59.24	51.63
6	63.48	74.32	71.60	63.28
7	77.20	85.21	83.28	86.21
8	84.52	89.26	90.14	95.18

Fig- : 4 In vitro drug release of various formulations

All the four batches of formulation F4 were found to release the drug in 8 h. The cumulative percentage release was found to be 95.18 %.

Stability studies

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the tablets of formulation F-4 after 3 months. Parameters quantified at various time intervals were shown;

Table- : 5 Results of stability studies of optimized formulation F-4

Formulation Code	Parameters	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-4	25 ^o C/60%RH % Release	95.18	94.25	93.15	93.12	Not less than 85 %
F-4	30 ^o C/75% RH % Release	95.18	94.24	93.12	93.10	Not less than 85 %
F-4	40 ^o C/75% RH % Release	95.18	94.21	93.11	93.08	Not less than 85 %

4. CONCLUSION:

The present study was aimed for preparation of niosomes. The niosomal suspension was prepared by the thin film technique, by varying ratios of span 20, Tween 20 and cholesterol and The prepared four formulations were evaluated for various parameters. Among the various formulations, the combination F4 was found to be most suitable because of its high encapsulation efficiency with a smaller particle size. The formulation F4 comprising phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol and span-20 fulfills the requirement of good niosomal formulation. *In vitro* drug release up to 8 hrs and more than 94.28% drug was released. Follows Zero order release kinetics. Cisplatin possesses all requisite qualities required for niosomal drug delivery.

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